

DInSAR deformation measurement using active and passive reflectors

G. Luzi, P.F. Espín-López, M. Crosetto, O. Monserrat, A. Barra, Q. Gao
Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC/CERCA), Division of Geomatics,
Av. Gauss 7, E-08860 Castelldefels, Barcelona, Spain

ABSTRACT

Passive Corner Reflectors (PCR) are often used in spaceborne SAR interferometry as benchmarks. The main goal of the use of PCRs in DInSAR deformation monitoring is to provide pixels with a high and stable response to be used as reference to estimate the deformation when natural persistent scatters are not available. The use of PCRs at C band is not always suitable, especially in areas as glaciers, snow covered regions, and mountain slopes, where accessibility and PCRs' installation can be very time and cost consuming, or where harsh weather conditions can jeopardize their performance. An alternative to PCRs is Active Reflectors (AR), more compact and lighter apparatus, which need a power source, and are often susceptible to the natural air temperature variations which can affect the stability of their response. The study presented here reports on the use of an AR designed to operate with Sentinel-1 SAR data, installed with some PCRs aimed at comparing the performance of the two approaches. The AR was designed and implemented to provide a fair performance/cost benefit to make feasible the setup of a dense network. Images covering almost one year have been processed to compare the performance of a prototype installed close to our center. A real campaign was also carried out installing an AR together with a network of PCRs in a site, located in a mountain area of Andorra, where a landslide occurred in 2018, and where a monitoring based on DInSAR is ongoing.

Keywords: Radar, SAR, interferometry, corner reflector, deformation.

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of artificial reflectors to assist Sentinel-1 interferometric processing in deformation monitoring is not a novelty. Passive Corner Reflectors (PCR) are often used in spaceborne SAR interferometry as standard ground points. Active Reflectors (AR) have also been investigated [1][2], but so far their use has not spread. The study presented here reports on the implementation and test of an AR designed to operate with Sentinel-1 SAR data, installed with some PCRs aimed at comparing their performance. The device is a low-cost AR designed according to a trade-off between performance and cost, which could be available to cover low coherence areas. The operative tests described here is based on the joint use of PCRs and a prototype of the proposed AR to assess the advantages and limitations of the use of this AR, and evaluate the benefit of a combined use of these two artificial reflectors. The working principle of the AR, graphically described by fig. 1a, is simple: when the satellite passes overhead, the AR receives the Radar signal and retransmits it with a higher strength, using the energy of the power source to amplify its signal, making its response stronger than the surrounding targets/clutter. Technical details about the prototype are available in [3]. The stability of its amplitude and phase response, which is fundamental for a successful employ, is basically affected by the presence of active Radio Frequency components that are sensitive to temperature changes. Some products have been made available from the market for field campaigns, but till now their use has not yet spread. Results concerning the phase stability of the AR in two different experimental campaigns are presented in this study. To improve with a-posteriori approach the stability of the retrieved phase response of the AR when the temperature varies along the monitoring temporal interval, a calibration curve was derived using a data acquisition carried out in a controlled environment.

The first test was carried out installing an AR close to the campus of the university UPC (Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya), nearby the city of Barcelona (Spain), where stable buildings can be used as a reference to check the AR response; here we briefly report the final outcomes of this experiment described in detail in [3]. The second campaign was carried out within the MOMPA project (Monitoring of Ground Movements and Action Protocol [4]) activities focused on the landslide event of La Portalada (Andorra) that occurred in 2019. Today the slope shows a slow movement that could affect a main road located at the bottom of the valley. Fig.1b and fig. 1c show pictures of the installed AR and

PCR respectively. In the following two sections the two campaigns will be described focusing on the second dedicated to the landslide monitoring. A brief conclusions section completes the manuscript. Measurement campaigns AT THE CAMPUS

In order to estimate the performances of the AR in a real situation, a prototype and a PCR, rectangular side trihedral with a 0.65 m size, were installed on 22 October 2019, in an agricultural field close to institute location. Both reflectors were oriented to receive the Sentinel-1A and -1B signals in the descending orbit geometry. The AR (Latitude: 41.276895, Longitude: 1.986798) and the PCR (Latitude: 41.277137, Longitude: 1.986031) are still operating in July 2021. Here we recall the final outcomes related to the phase stability achieved by the AR comparing its phase response with that measured in stable points as the PCR and some buildings close to it, representing an optimum phase stable reference. These data are obtained through a standard interferometric processing, which covers almost a period of one year.

To estimate the AR phase stability, we plotted the cumulated displacements versus the dates of acquisition in Figure 3. The figure shows a set of 55 Sentinel-1 images, in SLC IW mode, descending orbit (# 37), and VV pol, covering the period from 24 October 2019 to 18 September 2020. The results have been corrected based on the air temperatures, through a specific calibration function [3]. We have used the temperatures measured at 6:00 a.m. GMT, few minutes before the satellite passes, from a meteorological station located few kilometers far from the test site. The virtual deformation measured by the AR, caused by its thermal instability, is very close to the design requirements (± 2 mm), as shown in Figure 3. Thanks to the correction formula, the bias and the standard deviation calculated over the entire period is changed from -2.6 mm and 3 mm to -2.0 mm and 1.6 mm, respectively [3]. Measurement campaign in andorra

On August 10, 2019, the main access to Andorra from Spain, through La Seu d'Urgell, was stopped due to a rapid landslide occurred in the morning at the Portalada (Sant Julià de Lòria), in an area next to an important shopping center. The landslide forced the closure of traffic in both directions. The Andorran authorities reopened traffic in both directions after more than 6 hours. The sliding of the Portalada slope is the most important known phenomenon in the territory covered by the MOMPA project. For this reason, it was decided to analyze this area in detail using the InSAR technique. The InSAR study of the area required the deployment of a network of artificial reflectors due to the scarce presence of natural persistent scatters: the area surrounding the road is fully vegetated. The reflectors are oriented according to the acquisition geometry of the used Sentinel-1 data. In fig. 4 we show the measured points associated to the AR and some PCRs installed on the slope of La Portalada; the reference building used for InSAR processing is also shown.

The estimation of the deformations from the SAR images has been made using the PSIG software adapted to the study area, for details see [5]. 33 images and 122 interferograms, with a maximum temporal baseline of 30 days, were processed. The observed period starts on December 4, 2020 and ends on June 14, 2021. The shopping center area has a good response with many points, most of which are stable (green color). In fig. 5 we show three time series obtained from the interferometric processing of the pixels corresponding to the AR, and two PCRs with a different trend. The AR data have a moderate dispersion, and it maintains stable within ± 2 mm, while the CR4 indicates a trend of about 2 mm/month and CR9 is faster, with a velocity of approximately 6 mm/month.

Of note that, due to the high strength of the AR response, higher than that of PCR, a more stable and accurate phase estimate is achieved through the active device. In the analyzed period, except for the last day of June, the air temperature maintained low (-0.5 to 8.5) and this also foster a good stability of the AR without the need to correct the raw values.

2. CONCLUSIONS

Two preliminary tests have been carried out to evaluate the use of a low-cost active reflector for Sentinel-1 DInSAR joined by conventional passive corner reflectors. The experiment consists in a controlled experiment in a stable are, and the second is based on the monitoring of a slope recently affected by a landslide. The response of the AR compared to passive corner reflectors of moderate size is satisfactory, especially in situations where the environment is not favorable to passive corner reflectors. The estimated stability of the used prototype confirms the potential of a combined use of the two different reflectors.

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Figure 1. (a) Working principle of the active reflector; pictures of the AR (b) and a PCR (c) installed in the Andorra site.

Figure 2. (a) Google map view of the campus area where the reflectors are installed. (b) Sentinel-1B, VV SAR amplitude image in radar coordinates acquired on May 8, 2020. The labeled pixels correspond to the artificial reflectors and the campus buildings used as reference in the interferometric processing [3].

Figure 3. Cumulated deformation of the AR installed in the Campus after the correction based on an empirical function [3].

Figure 4: Position of the PCR network indicated by the corresponding pixels included in the orange rectangle. The sky-blue circle indicates the position of the AR. The red arrow indicates the position of the building taken as reference.

Figure 5: Deformation measured in three different targets: AR (a), stable PCR (b) and moving PCR (c).